

Self-mentions in persuasive writing in L2 French: a study on the use of JE, NOUS and ON by L1 Turkish learners

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Self-mentions are metadiscourse markers that are mostly expressed through the use of personal pronouns such as I and we. Their use generally results from a “conscious choice by writers to adopt a particular stance and a contextually situated authorial identity” (Hyland, 2005 : 53). Self-mentions in L1 Turkish students' writing in L1 and L2 English has been studied (Akbas, 2013), but there is no existing research on L1 Turkish writers in L2 French.

In French, in addition to the personal pronouns "je" (I) and "nous" (we), the indefinite pronoun "on" can sometimes be used as an equivalent to nous and therefore may express self-mention. How do Turkish learners of French employ self-mentions in argumentative writing, in comparison with native French writers ?

Our learner corpus is composed of 30 essays written by B1-level learners and 30 essays written by B2-level learners. All learners are first and second year university students. The reference corpus is composed of 30 essays written by native French students. Two prompts were used : the first is to write a formal letter to the mayor to persuade them not to cancel a concert ; the other is to write an email to other students to raise funds for a kitchen garden, on behalf of a student association. In addition to the occurrences of je and nous, we analysed each occurrence of on and only counted the ones that can be interpreted as self-mentions. In order to take into account the length of the essays, we calculated the relative frequency of these occurrences.

Results indicate that native French writers prefer the singular pronoun "je" in the formal letter task, whereas they tend to use "nous" in the email task. They rarely use "on" in either task. L1 Turkish learners use self-mentions more frequently than native writers. Learners overuse the "on" pronoun. This overuse diminishes at B2-level. The overuse of self-mentions in comparison with native writers may be the result of inappropriate teaching or hypercorrection. The overuse of "on", especially in formal letters, should be interpreted as misuse.

References

Akbas, E. (2013). Are They Discussing in the Same Way? Interactional Metadiscourse in Turkish Writers' Texts. In Łyda, A., Warchał, K. (eds) *Occupying Niches: Interculturality, Cross-culturality and Aculturality in Academic Research. Second Language Learning and Teaching*. (pp. 119-133). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-02526-1_8

Hyland, K. (2005). *Metadiscourse : Exploring Interaction in Writing*. Bloomsbury Publishing Plc.